

Determinants of Career Paths Development in the University System
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Editor's Note

In December 1963, the United Nations General Assembly adopted resolution to explore ways and means of supporting national efforts for the eradication of illiteracy, through a world campaign, and any other appropriate measures, both financial and non-financial. Following this resolution, UNESCO convened a number of regional conferences to study the problem of illiteracy in different countries. In April, 1964, it convened an international committee of experts on literacy, which suggested the selective approach that would launch literacy programmes in organized sections of the economy, particularly in such areas where people in employment would need literacy for their regular work; the implication was that national development plans embracing economic and general educational considerations should include programmes for functional management. The concept of functional management was thus formulated within a context in which the world was ready for a new approach to literacy. Its historical roots portray it as born by the necessity for urgent development. This places functional literacy in the position of endearment to all developing countries as a method of promoting adjustment to desirable change, so that all peoples in a development situation may grow to become the agents and the objects of their own development.

One of the great aims of functional management makes its adherent a better of what he is. Thus, its adoption helps anybody engaged in any development-oriented work to become more competent and better equipped for his work. Thus the farmer, artisan, industrial worker, trader, teacher, office worker and in fact, anybody in a development situation, require functionality to become better able to perform their tasks. The fact is that the recasting of the modes of functioning in a modern economy, the creation of a new mentality, the process of adaptation to the industrial environment and the ability to meet its technical demands, all require some level of functional management.

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Determinants of Career Paths Development in the University System

by

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Abstract

This paper appraised the Determinants of career paths development. It discusses the definition (i) of Career Paths (ii). Career Path Component (iii) Career Planning and Management for Organisation (iv) Career Competencies (v) Building and Managing Competencies (vi) Methods of Achieving Creativity in Career Path/Direction (vii) Motivational Techniques and Tools used in Career Path/ Direction (viii) Effect of Motivation in Career Path/Direction. The paper concludes that motivation is very important in any working environment to achieve a successful and a sustainable career path development.

Definition of Career as a Path

The term career is often defined as the unfolding sequence of a person's work experiences over time Arthur, Hall, & Lawrence, 1989a, 1989b;

Hughes, 1958) within an occupational or organisational context (Van Maanen & Barley, 1984). This definition reflects the path metaphor, approaching career as a journey or as movement (Inkson, 2004). This metaphor incorporates two key underlying facets of career: time and direction (Adamson, Doherty, & Viney, 1998; Inkson, 2004) that reflect the global manager's career of multiple moves towards different locations and positions.

The definition of career as a path explicitly embraces an evolution over time, a series of career moves. This career definition as a sequence of moves' acknowledges the trend that organisations no longer provide fixed career paths. Employees no longer pursue lifetime employment and security within a single organisational context. Rather, organisations provide bounded

"opportunities for development" and managers take on new, bounded opportunities when they appear (Herriot & Pemberton, 1995; Rousseau,

1996). Global managers are especially confronted with a series of career moves as they are expected to fulfil multiple short-term assignments and undertake frequent travels. Each of these moves may reflect different skills and experiences gained, relationships nurtured, and opportunities encountered (Arthur & Rousseau, 1996a, 1996b; Robinson & Miner, 1996).

Conceptualising a global career as a series of moves consequently implies that research on each particular career move can contribute to our understanding of how global managers' motivations and opportunities for development change with new circumstances and over time.

The notion of career as a path implies a route which one is following, having a direction or a purpose that links the successive positions over time (Adamson et al., 1998). As managers are moving away from single employment settings, career paths are no longer unidirectional up the hierarchical ladder. It is no longer apparent how an overall career path can be logical and purposeful because career moves can be upwards, downwards, forwards, backwards, sideways or idiosyncratic (Baruch, 2004; Inkson, 2004).

The multi-directional nature of a career path implies that the notion of internal career or the subjective sense of where one is going in work life (Schein,

1996) becomes important to provide logic to the overall path. This characteristic also applies to global managers as their different career moves can go world-wide in different directions, each having a different purpose.

Conceptualising a global career as a path in multiple directions consequently implies that research on the overall route can contribute to our understanding of how global managers make sense of the different moves.

According to Eaton and Bailyn (2000), career paths are embedded in a number of intersecting cycles, of which the organisation is no longer the predominant one. The diminishing role of organisations in constituting career paths is also acknowledged in recent career theory Arthur & Rousseau, 1996a, 1996b), placing personal life which evolves in intersection with economic characteristics (Eaton & Bailyn, 2000) in the foreground. In the case of global managers, these economic characteristics resemble the complex global environment (Rhinesmith, 1996) which instigates us to map global career paths as an intersection of three domains: an individual, organisational, and global environment domain. Inspired by Eaton and Bailyn's

(2000) conception of career, we suggest the following definition of a global career path, adding the global environment domain. A global career path can be considered "as a series of initiatives and adaptations to employment, family and different communities, evolving with changes in individual interests or skills, life experiences of oneself and the people central to one's personal space (individual domain), the characteristics and requirements of one's contemporary employment context (organisational domain) and the encountered economic pressures, technological opportunities and cultural values of the global context (global environment domain)."

Wanous (1980) also suggested that some incumbents may accept a position primarily to gain entry into a particular organisation because of the expectation of upward promotion. The importance of providing career path information has become increasingly apparent in recent years because of a number of factors.

These include work force demographic shifts, slow economic growth, budgetary deficits, and technological change. All of these factors have, conspired to vastly reduce the possibility of upward career mobility.

With the declining possibility of upward promotion, organisations increasingly recognize the need for a broader approach to career development (Latack & Dozier, 1986). A good place to begin in this broader approach is to confront the unrealistic expectations that prospective employees have about promotion, expectations which persist from an era when there was a relative shortage of managerial talent. Career development models are paying increasing attention to the importance of the availability of career information and the ability of individuals to make use of such information in formulating career decisions (Caldwell & Compton, 1984;

Roas, 1987; Hall, 1976; London, 1983; Mihal, Source, & Compte, 1984; Rhodes & Doering, 1983; Rosenbaum, 1979). London (1983), for example, theorises that the completeness and accuracy of information about career opportunities is a key factor underlying career motivation, and that inferior information, misconceptions, or inaccurate interpretation of information may result in poor decisions and/or inappropriate or dysfunctional behaviours.

Career Planning and Management for Organisational Development

Career planning and management can be carried out at two levels within the organisational level. The traditional approach was a situation in which organisations rather than the individual determined the career pursuits of their employees as they knew, so they seem to claim, what was best for the employees.

However, with increasing rate of unemployment, recession and downturn in the economy and industrial activities every employee was responsible for his or her career planning. This appears to be the state of things with respect to organisational attitude to career planning and management in Nigeria today.

With the continued restructuring of the industries and commercial sector of the economy there should be a shift of position from the laissez-faire attitudes of entrepreneurs toward a balance path of career planning and management involving both the organisations and the Individual managers but without removing final responsibility from the latter.

Career development for individuals is a vital prerequisite for organisational development. To prepare for organisational change which necessarily occurs organisation need committed people. They should therefore develop managers who would not only implement change but handle the consequences of change perfectly in their own and others' benefit.

In specific terms Miller (1997) stated that the primary reason for organisational interest in managing career is to increase profit and productivity.

It is therefore a matter of logic that those who would bring about the desired profits and productivity are adequately centered by having among others a fulfilling career.

Employer's interest in career planning and management should be based on the need to:

- a) Plan human resources enhancement to guarantee organisational development, survival and future company success.
- b) Improve the match between the individual and work, enhance productivity and reflect an understanding of human needs so as to create an environment of work quality that attracts and rewards employees.
- c) Understand the changing work ethics and social values that require a more participative, more adaptive working environment where the employee is a partner in progress.
- d) Recognise evidence of increased career frustration in valuable professional and management employees who feel their progress has been stalled.

Career Planning and Management Programmes

Organisations wishing to pursue a career planning and management programmes have a diverse choice of programmes to select from as suggested below:

- a) Career counselling through interviews to be conducted by managers. Professional counsellors or psychologists within and outside the Organisation.
- b) Workshops, seminars and conferences designed to assist the individual in goal setting and establishing action plans for change.
- c) Organisational development and job design and development programmes that aim at restructuring work for improved personal growth and enhanced job satisfaction.
- d) Programs designed to assist the individual in self-assessment and increased self-understanding.
- e) Programmes designed to communicate opportunities such as dictionary of occupational titles, listings, posting to job opening etc.
- f) Educational and experimental programmes that prepare the individual with skill and knowledge of new activities and new career or that assist in enhancing capability for the current job.
- g) Management training or. career counselling.
- h) Career information centers with information about company jobs and carer paths including current literature on career planning,

- i) Child and family care provision
- j) Improved promotion policies k.
- k) Compensation and benefits.

Whatever the career planning programmes established by organisations. Organisations must ensure their success by carrying out the following activities.

a. Goal setting and communication: Goals should be set at two levels of the organization. Individual level and global (Organisational) level.

Management should be clear about their goal and communicate such to individuals who in planning for personal change and growth incorporate the direction of the organisation for then would career planning and management result in organisational development. There must be a fit between the goals of the individual and (that of the) organisation.

b. Human-resource planning: A good human resource plan helps to support individual career development. Human-resources planning or manpower planning is the process of accomplishing organisational objectives by acquiring, retaining, terminating, developing and properly using the human resources in an organisation (Obikoya 1996).

c. Climate setting: Healthy planning for careers within the organisation can only take place in a positive, supportive, co-operative and participative aimate, management's policy on career planning must be supported by action.

d. Education: Well trained and educated workforce serves as impetus for career planning.

e. Performance appraisal and feedback: Performance appraisal is the term used to describe a variety of techniques by which superiors, peers, subordinate and the individual employees themselves rate, rank or describe the employees' work effectiveness Performance appraisal is necessary to establish a base in reality for career planning. To plan change and growth the employee must know what is expected of him and how he is presently doing it.

f. Organisation and job development; good career planning should start with organisational redesign to improve quality of work and general fit between employees and the company.

Formulation of Career Growth for Employees

The bases of all career planning and management programmes are career goals for individual employees. Organisations have a role to help employees select and formulate their career goals. Goals selection and formulation are the heart of the targeting stage in Kaye's (1980) six stage model of career management. According to him, effective career management involves an individual moving successively through each of the following stages.

- a) Profiling: The individual at this stage is made up of abilities, aptitudes, self-awareness, individual uniqueness, goals, intelligence, emotions, need for achievement and need for others. These variables of the individual must be profiled or assessed in terms of strength and weakness.
- b) Reality testing: This involves determining how others assess one's strength and awareness and assessing the pertinent environmental realities which enhances or constrains one's opportunities.
- c) Targeting: Selecting and formulating career goals based on the assessment of the first two stated above.
- d) Strategising: Developing action plans to carry out the established goals.
- e) Execution: Putting these action plans to work
- f) Integration: Reaping the rewards of the execution stage

Building and Managing Morale to Boost Career Path Development

The following are some techniques used by organisation to build high morale in career path development.

- i. Utilisation of suggestion schemes and open door policies.
- ii. Team building i.e. management of the work group as a team rather than as individuals leads to recognition of a common feature among groups, cohesion and solidarity hence his level of morale.
- iii. Adopting measures aimed at motivating subordinates. iv. Encouraging participation to boost the morale of individuals.

- iv. Organisational development methods that aim to modify individual behaviour overtime.

It should be noted that successful utilisation of these techniques depends on the creation of a favourable organisational climate. Good morale cannot be developed on an unsound base of dissatisfaction with fundamental aspects of the organisation.

Individual domain

As part of the individual domain, we identified three factors that distinctively point to the changing nature of global careers: career competencies, locus of career development responsibility, and the boundary between work and personal life. These individual factors are discussed within the boundary-less career literature, where they are well-accepted (Arthur & Rousseau, 1996a, 1996b; Eaton & Bailyn, 2000), as well as in the global management literature.

Career competencies

Within the career literature (Arthur, Claman, & Defilippi, 1995; Defilippi & Arthur, 1994, 1996), it is argued that competency accumulation occurs at the level of the individual. Each form of knowledge dynamically changes in response to shifting environmental, employment and personal variables.

Personal competencies reflect these forms of knowing, introducing three different career competencies: knowing-why, knowing-how, and knowing-

Knowing-Why competencies answer the question 'Why?' as it relates to career motivation and personal meaning (Defilippi & Arthur, 1994). Career scholars (Mirvis & Hall, 1996; Mohrman & Cohen, 1995) tend to discuss this competency in terms of the individual identifying personally with work rather than with the organisation.

Source: Arthur M.B & Rossneau D.M 1996

Methods of Achieving Creativities in Career Paths Development

Brainstorming: Spontaneous attempt to come with ideas by individuals interacting in a free environment.

- i. Synetics: This entails the joining of different and irrelevant elements to arrive, at ideas.
- ii. Norminal Grouping: A creative technique that involves coming up with ideas by means of highly structured procedures that purposely attempt to restrict verbal interaction.

Achievement of creative thinking in an organisation is dependent on

- i. Knowledge of individuals in organisation.
- ii. Availability of time for creative thinking.
- iii. Establishment of rules, procedures and policies that foster creative thinking.
- iv. Internal arrangements include minimal bureaucracy, reasonable working condition and easy communication.
- v. Backgrounds of people in an organisation also count on creative thinking and Career Paths. In other words, mixed backgrounds in terms of academics racial and cultural settings of people in organisation.

Challenges to Career Path Development

- i. The factors that constrain creative thinking in organisation are:
- ii. Strict adherence to bureaucratic principles.
- iii. Communication breakdown. Lack of analytical equipments.
- iv. Existence of non-relevant uniformity.
- v. Lack of information between vertical and horizontal levels.
- vi. Lack of recognition for ideas which come from a team, rather than individual.

External Factors

The factors imposed on the organisation from the outside are more embracing and beyond the control of the organisation. These factors include:

- i. The economic environment
- ii. The changing technology
- iii. The forces of competition
- iv. Legal constraint,
- v. Changes within the international environment,

The motivational tools and techniques used in Career Path Development include:

- a) Job Enrichment
- b) Participation in Decision-Making
- c) Job Enlargement
- d) Promotion
- e) Authority and Accountability
- f) Career Development
- g) Money

Job Enrichment

As a motivational technique Job enrichment emphasised the need to make jobs more challenging and meaningful. Furthermore Job enrichment is consistent with the motivation factor of Herzberg's two-factor theory of motivation.

Flippo, (1988) a job could be enriched by:

- i. Introducing variety into the job content.
- ii. Giving workers more latitude in decision-making.
- iii. Giving workers feelings of personal responsibilities.
- iv. Ensuring that workers see how their efforts contribute to company's progress.

- v. Giving workers feedback on their performance,
- vi. Involving workers in external and internal changes in the work environment.

Inegbenebor (1982) posited that one of the important goals of management development is to ensure that competent and trained individuals are always available for executive positions as the organisation grows.

To attract and retain such individuals requires the provision of competitive rewards, definition of career paths by which the personal goals of the individual may be attained within the organisation, significant and meaningful work experience, and the enhancement of the employee's perceptions of the organisation as a stable and fair employer.

In continuation, he adds that, having dealt with the problem of attracting suitable managers into the organisation, the issue that needs attention now is the extent to which the organization is able to retain the managerial personnel and the opportunities for advancement provided within the organisation. In conclusion, he stated that the factors, along with a favourable perception of the organisation as a fair employer, will enable the employees to expect a rewarding over a long period of time. Where these conditions exist, the employee will be encouraged to develop, and nurture the skills and attitudes required for satisfactory performance Inegbenebor (1982).

(b) Participation

Participation implies that workers are consulted or allowed to take part in decision-making on matters that affect them. Participation has been identified as one of the major techniques of motivation in Career Path Development according to Flippo (1988) the objectives of participation are three-fold, namely: Ethical or social, political, and economic. Therefore, the more the employees are allowed in decision-making, the more they would be motivated towards improved performance on the job.

(1) Ethical/Social

In the ethical or social context, Ekpenyong (1992) stated that participation is designed to promote individual development in accordance with the conception of human rights, and from ILO (1985) Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which states that:

- All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and should act towards one another in the spirit of brotherhood - Article 2.
- Everyone, as a member of the society, is entitled to the realization of the economic rights indispensable for his dignity and the free development of his personality - Article 22.

(ii) Political

In the political context, participation is generally considered under the description of industrial democracy. Here, Ekpenyong argues that, in a democratic system, workers have the same political rights as citizens within the organisation where they work to decide on issues affecting them, just as every eligible citizen during an election has the right to vote.

(iii) Economic

Participation in the economic context relates directly or indirectly to increasing the efficiency of the organisation. The argument here, according to Ekpenyong, is that, by associating the workers with the decisions taken, it is possible to improve the quantity and quality of output and the utilisation of labour, raw materials and equipment, as well as the introduction of new techniques. Another argument is that the experience and intelligence of those who actually do the work will be fully tapped and this will greatly improve the organisation and methods of operation.

In his contribution, Banjoko (1996) affirms that management would benefit from an enormous amount of hitherto untapped reserves of human energy through workers' involvement in decision-making, and this will greatly enhance employee-employer co-operation.

(C) Job Enlargement

According to Ogunwonyi (1982) a job is enlarged when additional elements are added to the horizontal job content thereby lengthening the work cycle which will require additional skills

and provide a greater sense of accomplishment and task identity. He also argues that job enlargement is useful to a staff whose energies are not fully utilised on one job, but possesses the potentials to handle more tasks which would be beneficial to the staff and to the company as productivity increases. Job enlargement will reduce monotony, and increase employee motivation on the job.

(d) Promotion

According to Ubeku (1983) employees want to see a change for the better in their place of work. For example, a clerk would like to become a senior clerk and a salesman a senior salesman. Promotion brings along with it not just more money but a mark of recognition of the individual's performance.

Consequently, in order to justify this recognition, the promoted employee puts in more effort in his work.

Ubeku concludes that promotion puts a new life in the individual and activates his knowledge, skills, attitudes etc, and in consequence, he strives harder to be more effective in his new job, thereby making the motivating effect of promotion high,

(e) Authority and Accountability

Ubeku believes that one of the major factors in motivating a job-holder is to give him increased authority hold him accountable for the results.

According to him, the situation will pose a challenge to which the job-holder will react.

(f) Career Development

Career development is a strong and positive motivational technique. In the Nigerian situation, there are organisations where the chief executives and senior managers rose through the ranks. Such organisations are those that have very effective career development programmes for both the existing and incoming employees.

(g) Money

As a motivator, money comes in the form of wages/salary, fringe benefits, bonuses, pension schemes and other forms of incentives. Money, therefore, can never be overlooked as a major motivator, especially in countries with a low per capital income like Nigeria, To the most senior managers, money will ensure a comfortable house, a suitable car, a comfortable life after

retirement, amongst other benefits. To the lower managers and other ranks, monetary compensation, is also valued for life sustenance. Therefore, money could be used as a tool of motivation.

Situational Approach to Motivation

A situational approach to motivation implies that one theory or technique of motivation cannot be applied to all kinds of situations. This is because people are different. This has prompted Koontz, Donnel and Weithrich [1980] to conclude that what a manager or management does to induce individual efforts to accomplish organisational objectives must clearly take into account the differences between individuals, groups and organisational climates. The application of motivation techniques should, therefore, be based on prevailing situations.

Effects of Motivation on Career Path Development

A person could be highly or poorly motivated. That is, motivation could be high or low. High motivation could produce the following positive results:

- Willingness and co-operation towards organisational objectives
- Loyalty to the organisation and its leadership.
- Good discipline and conformity to rules.
- Seeking for tasks where a person can exercise personal responsibility.
- A high interest in the organisation.
- A good job performance and personal initiative.
- A display of initiatives and willingness to take action.
- A consistent desire for achievement.

It seems logical to mention that an organisation will suffer and not be able to attain given objectives if its staff are poorly motivated. This will be due to:

- Lack of willing co-operation towards organisational objective.
- Lack of loyalty to the organisation and its leadership.

- Engaging in acts of indiscipline resulting in lack of conformity with rules.
- Doing just enough to retain the job.
- Low interest in the organisation,
- Low performance and lack of interest in using personal initiative
- Low interest in unreactive behaviour.
- Giving just enough effort for the demand of the test.

Conclusion

For an organisation to achieve an effective and efficient career path the following prescriptions are hereby recommended.

- i. The employee in selecting a career goal must identify the variety of options available to him both within and outside the organisation.
- ii. He must also evaluate the desirability and practicability of each of the options. There are at least five career options available to an individual. He may move vertically on the same job by moving from a lower position to (the next) higher position. He may also move laterally across function as for example, moving from the production department to the marketing department. The employee also has a realignment or downward movement career option by moving to a lesser position within the same organisation.
- iii. In addition, the job can be enriched by creating more challenges on the present job. Finally, he may at the last resort, consider relocating out of the organisation.

Once career options have been identified and selected the goal/objective formulation process must begin, whatever the goals formulae, each must be specific, measurable, agreed, realistic, time bound and trackable.

On a final note, the sustenance of the vision and mission of any university does not lie with the management alone, neither does it rest with academic staff nor non-academic staff. It is simply a collective efforts of all the stakeholders.

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